

Strategic Sourcing and Supplier Relationship Management in Food and Beverage Firms in Rivers State.

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between strategic sourcing and supplier relationship management in food and beverage firms located in Rivers State. Strategic sourcing was employed as the explanatory variable and treated as a single-dimensional construct, while supplier relationship management served as the dependent variable, measured through supplier collaboration and information sharing. A cross-sectional survey design was adopted, targeting twelve (12) food and beverage firms within the state. Five (5) copies of the research instrument were administered to each firm, yielding a total of sixty (60) respondents. Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire based on a 5-point Likert scale. The hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation, and the data were analyzed with SPSS version 25.0. Findings revealed a positive and significant relationship between strategic sourcing and supplier relationship management. The study concluded that strategic sourcing significantly enhances supplier relationship management in food and beverage firms in Rivers State. It is therefore recommended that firms in the industry adopt effective supplier relationship management practices to boost both operational efficiency and financial performance.

Keywords: Sourcing Strategy, Supplier relationship management, supplier collaboration, Information Sharing

INTRODUCTION

In recent times, Nigeria has been grappling with harsh economic realities, characterized by severe competition, policy uncertainties, and volatile market conditions. These factors have compounded the complexity of the business environment, further exacerbated by global environmental concerns that demand sustainable business practices. As organizations strive to adapt to these changes, sourcing decisions have emerged as critical components, significantly influencing production efficiency and overall organizational performance. In light of these developments, Wang et al. (2020) assert that strategic sourcing forms a fundamental aspect of a firm's strategic decision-making process. It necessitates the integration of procurement, logistics, operations, and marketing functions to ensure operational synergy. Jum'a (2020) complements this view by emphasizing that suppliers play a vital role in enhancing supply chain performance. Therefore, managing supplier relationships effectively and efficiently is essential for achieving competitive advantage.

Building on this, Amoako-Gyampah et al. (2019) highlight the importance of aligning purchasing strategies with supplier relationship management (SRM) efforts to improve performance outcomes. Al-Zubaidi (2019) further argues that SRM is pivotal in reducing costs, enhancing efficiency, and driving supply chain performance. He underscores its relevance in today's globally competitive market, where organizations aim to deliver low-cost, high-quality products. Similarly, Hughes and Wadd (n.d.) maintain that SRM, when properly implemented, can deliver substantial business benefits. However, this requires a comprehensive understanding and company-wide commitment. Nurazyiyati (2019) provides a more integrative perspective, describing SRM as a holistic approach that involves both buyers and sellers. He contends that SRM cannot be confined to the procurement department alone; rather, it should be implemented across the entire organization, utilizing defined processes, principles, tools, and communication strategies to manage supplier relationships throughout the supplier lifecycle. Numerous empirical studies have explored the dimensions of strategic sourcing. For instance, Chen and Guo (2014) investigated strategic sourcing within uncertain supply chains and under retail competition. Ondoro (2015) developed a framework for strategic purchasing and its implications for supply chain management. Kihanya, Wafula, Onditi, and Munene (2015) examined the influence of strategic sourcing on organizational performance using Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and

Technology as a case study. More recently, Jum'a (2021) studied the role of strategic sourcing in mitigating the uncertainties of the manufacturing sector during the COVID-19 pandemic. Despite the wealth of literature on strategic sourcing and SRM, there remains a noticeable gap in context-specific investigations, particularly within the food and beverage sector in Rivers State, Nigeria. Consequently, this study seeks to fill this gap by examining the nexus between strategic sourcing and supplier relationship management in food and beverage firms located in Rivers State.

Study Variable and Research Framework

Study variables unveil the direction of the research work. They serve as the skeletal structure upon which the entire work is built. This study has two major variables strategic sourcing which is the explanatory variable and it is treated as a single unit variable. Supplier relationship management as the explained variable with collaboration and information sharing as measures is depicted below in Figure 1.

Fig 1 Conceptual Framework for Strategic Sourcing and Supplier Relationship Management in Food and Beverage Firms in Rivers State.

Source: (Authors Conceptualization 2024).

The following null hypotheses were developed for the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between strategic sourcing and collaboration

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between strategic sourcing and information sharing

Theoretical foundation

The systems theory was developed by Ludwig von Bertalanffy (1968). Bertalanffy suggests that the success of an organization depends on several key elements: synergy, interdependence, and interrelations between various subsystems. According to Bertalanffy (1968), a system is a combination of factors that work together to give a result. Systems theory calls for addressing various parts of a system from a holistic viewpoint and not in isolation of each other in tackling the problems in their entirety. The theory advocates for greater understanding of the problems or issues at hand through gauging patterns or the interrelationships that are at play among various entities of a system (Rubenstein *et al.*, 2001). Systems theory enables the organization to manage the complexity of strategic sourcing by segmenting the sourcing process into small sub-sections, for example, supplier selection, contract management, risk management etc. while considering how these subsystems interact within the larger system.

Concept of Strategic Sourcing

Earlier scholars like Smeltzer et al. (2003) defined strategic sourcing as “a comprehensive process of buying all inputs to run a company’s operations as well as managing suppliers, to achieve long-term objectives. Lyons and Farrington (2006) define strategic sourcing as “concerned with the top-level, longer-term decision relating to high – profit, high supply risk items and low-profit, high supply risk bottleneck product and services”. It’s also concerned with the formulation of long-term purchasing policies, supplier base, partnership sourcing, reciprocal and intra-company trading, globalization and countertrade, the purchase of capital equipment and ethical issues. On their part, Su and Gargeya (2012) described strategic sourcing as a framework that uses suppliers' capabilities in the manufacturing process to achieve an organisation’s strategic objective. It is stated that sourcing costs represent 40 to 80 percent of the cost of goods sold, and 30 to 50 percent of revenues – a ratio that has remained constant in most industries for many years. Companies excelling in strategic sourcing save almost 10 to 20 times as much as it costs to operate their sourcing operations

Supplier Relationship Management

Scholars are in near consensus that supplier relationship management is a vital tool for achieving sustainable competitive advantage because of proliferating levels of surfacing within global supply chains, growing supply uncertainties, diverse customer requirements as well as demand uncertainties that companies face in the competitive environment surfacing within global supply chains, growing supply uncertainties, diverse customer requirements as well as demand uncertainties that companies face in the competitive environment (Amoako-Gyampah et al., 2019; Zhang & Cao, 2018). Akaman and Miller (2013) described supplier relationship management as the act of planning, implementing, developing and monitoring company relationships with current and potential suppliers. On their part, Schu et al. (2014) averred that supplier relationship management involves motivating supplying firms to act in such a way that organizational needs will be met; identifying suppliers that are important to the firm operation; and providing guidelines on how to work with different types of suppliers.

In simple terms, SRM is a comprehensive approach to managing an organization’s interactions with supplying firms in a win-win relationship where both parties benefit from the relationship. This relationship enhances a firm’s efficiency in terms of goods and service acquisition, inventory management and material processing (SAP, 2003). Supplier relationship management (SRM) is the discipline of strategically planning for, and managing, all interactions with third-party organizations that supply goods and/or services to an organization in order to maximize the value of those interactions. It entails creating closer, more collaborative relationships with key suppliers in order to uncover and realize new value and reduce risk.

Measures of Supplier Relationship Management

Supplier Collaboration

Collaboration among channel partners has been noted by scholars to entail looking for and capitalizing on the expertise and skill of individual firms to collectively provide benefits to end consumers. Fawcett, Magnan, and Ogden (2007) elaborated that the collaboration’s goal is to have all partners work together, solve problems, and provide better customer satisfaction as per their expectation level. According to Wilding and Wagner (2012), supplier collaboration is the working of two or more companies collectively to run supply chain operations and have better results as compared to when these firms work individually. On their part, Simatupang, Wright, and Sridharan (2002) established that supplier collaboration is “the joint working among two or more firms through a supply chain to meet end customers satisfaction and the basic purpose of the supplier collaboration is to optimize profit, for all chain partners and create a competitive edge”. Also, supplier collaboration has been defined as a “relational system in the common pool of resources; every member can use these resources to facilitate group or individual goals and was noted to be a key element of effective service, and it reduces the costs of entering the market and obtaining technological knowledge” (Friedman, Reynolds, Quan, Crusto & Kaufman, 2007).

Information Sharing

Khurana et al. (2011) aver that information sharing within a supply chain has numerous benefits among supply chain members, it reduces different types of uncertainties related to demand, product and technology that add costs to supply chain processes. Information sharing facilitates, the enhancing of the efficiency and effectiveness of the supply chain as it obtains certain advantages. Kumar et al. (2011) further highlighted more benefits of information sharing among supply chains including better coordination between different departments and between supply chain members and improved control of the supply chain processes, also which may reduce product design time, make the production lead-time shorter and stable the outputs along with reliable quality. Information sharing was defined by Simatupang and Sridharn (2001) as the process that facilitates data collection, documentation, and the storing, retrieving, and transferring of private information. Participating members may share information only if they have the willingness to do so; consequently, they should redesign their information structure in order to be able to assemble and transfer all private information to increase their capability to make better decisions. Based on the literature the significant benefit in our view is that information sharing increases the visibility between organizations which may lead to detecting problems earlier, reducing the cycle time from order to delivery as well as building and strengthening social bonds, especially in the presence of new social media

Empirical Review on Strategic Sourcing and Supplier Relationship Management

Jum'a (2021) examined the role of strategic sourcing in facing uncertainty in the manufacturing business environment. The study confirmed that there is a significant effect of internal integration and development of key suppliers on the operational performance of manufacturing firms during COVID-19. Chen et al. (2015) examined strategic sourcing in the presence of uncertain supply chains and retail competition. The result revealed that adopting a dual-sourcing strategy aids in mitigating supply risk and acts as an incentive for more effective retail competition. Kim and Chai (2014) investigated the role of strategic sourcing on organizational performance. The main objective of this study is to investigate the impact of organizational culture on supply chain risk and strategic sourcing. The findings revealed that organizational culture and strategic sourcing mitigate supply chain risks. Organizational culture also makes a positive impact on the implementation of strategic sourcing.

METHODOLOGY

This study on strategic sourcing and supplier relationship management adopted the cross-sectional survey research design. Data were collected through a questionnaire using a Likert five-point scale ranging from “strongly agree” to “strongly disagree”. The explanatory variable strategic sourcing was treated as a single unit variable while the explained variable supplier relationship management had supplier collaboration and information sharing as its measures. The population of the study comprised selected food and beverage firms in Rivers State. 5 copies of the research instrument were sent to the 12 selected food and beverage firms, the total number of respondents was sixty. The hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient with the aid of the Statistical Tool for Social Science (SPSS version 25.1).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Description of Levels of Relationship between Variables

Ranges of r with positive and negative Descriptive level relationship of r Sign values

+ .7 to 1.0	Very Strong
+ .6 to .69	Strong
+ .4 to .59	Moderate
+ .1 to .39	Weak

Source: Mangiafico, (2016)

The positive (+) sign in the values of r implies a direct/positive relationship, whereas the negative (-) of r implies an indirect/negative or inverse relationship between the two variables. This section continues by testing the hypotheses raised in section one of this study to determine the strength and direction of the relationship (if any) between the explanatory variable and the explained variable

Table 2: Research Instrument Distribution, Retrieval and Usage

S/N	Questionnaire	Quantity	Percentage (%)
1	Produced Copies	60	100
2	Distributed Copies	60	100
3	Retrieved Copies	54	90
4	Copies not retrieved	6	10

Source: Research Desk (2024)

The Statistics in Table 2 indicate that a total of 60 copies (100%) of the research instrument were produced but 54 copies (90%) were retrieved and 6 copies (10%) were not retrieved. Furthermore, the 60 copies (90%) distributed were useful. Which is a good figure to be used for the analysis.

Table 3 Descriptive Statistics on All the Study Variables

	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Strategic Sourcing	54	3615	4.75	3.603
Supplier collaboration	54	2082	4.1	3.206
Information Sharing	54	2226	4.5	4.163
Valid N (listwise)	54			

Source: SPSS Output, 2024

Table 3. Explains the descriptive statistics on the dimension of the explanatory variables and the measures of the explained variable The table shows the descriptive statistics on the measures of the criterion variables (supplier collaboration and information sharing). Specifically, Table 3 revealed that strategic sourcing has a mean of 4.75 and a standard deviation of 3.603. supplier collaboration has a mean of 4.1 and a standard deviation of 3.206. information sharing has a mean of 4.5 and a standard deviation of 4.163.

Decision Rule

Reject the null hypothesis (H0) if $PV < 0.05$ for a 2-tailed test and conclude that a significant relationship exists.

Table 4 Correlation Analysis on Strategic Sourcing and Supplier Collaboration (n= 54)

Pearson Correlation r.	Strategic Sourcing	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.954**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
	Supplier collaboration	Correlation Coefficient	.954**	1.000
		N	54	54
			Strategic Sourcing	Supplier collaboration
		N	54	54

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 above shows that the Pearson Correlation Coefficient ($r = 0.954^{**}$), this value is very high, implying that a very strong relationship exists between strategic sourcing and supplier collaboration. The positive sign of the correlation coefficient indicates a positive relationship. That is to say that supplier collaboration among suppliers is the hallmark of adopting strategic sourcing in the studied food and beverage firms. As shown in Table 4, the probability value is $(0.000) < (0.05)$ level of significance; hence the researcher rejects the null hypothesis and concludes that there is a significant, positive, and very strong relationship between strategic sourcing and supplier collaboration and antecedent of suppliers' relationship management

Table 5 Correlation Analysis on Strategic Sourcing and Information Sharing (n= 54)

		Strategic Sourcing	Information Sharing
Pearson Correlation r.	Strategic Sourcing	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.
		N	54
	Information Sharing	Correlation Coefficient	.970**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	54

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 5 above shows that the Pearson Correlation Coefficient ($r = 0.970^{**}$), this value is very high, implying that a strong relationship exists between strategic sourcing and information sharing. The positive sign of the correlation coefficient indicates a positive relationship. That is to say that suppliers' ability to share relevant information is associated with the adoption of strategic sourcing in the studied independent food and beverage firms. As shown in Table 5, the probability value is $(0.000) < (0.05)$ level of significance; hence the researcher rejects the null hypothesis and concludes that there is a significant relationship between strategic sourcing and information sharing.

The findings of this study showed that strategic sourcing has a strong influence on supplier collaboration. This is indicated by the Pearson Correlation Coefficient of 0.954, at a significant level of probability value ($PV = 0.000 < 0.05$ (2-tailed)). This implies a relationship of 95.4% of strategic sourcing with supplier collaboration of food and beverage firms in Rivers State.

This agrees with the research conducted by Su and Gargeya (2012) whose study showed that strategic sourcing is a framework that uses suppliers' capabilities in the manufacturing process to achieve an organisation's strategic objective. The second result from the analysis of the study showed that strategic sourcing has a strong influence on information sharing. This is indicated by the Pearson Correlation Coefficient of 0.970, at a significant level of probability value ($PV = 0.000 < 0.05$ (2-tailed)). This implies that 97.0% of strategic sourcing is related to information sharing of food and beverages in Rivers State. This position is supported by Kim and Chai (2014) who reported that strategic sourcing mitigates supply chain risks. Also, Simatupang, et al. (2002) reported that supplier collaboration allows firms to meet end customer satisfaction and the basic purpose of supplier collaboration is to optimize profit.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study and the consistency with results of similar studies, we conclude that value network alliance is an important driver of market visibility of Food and beverage in River State. It is stated that sourcing costs represent 40 to 80 percent of the cost of goods sold, and 30 to 50 percent of revenues a ratio that has remained constant in most industries for many years. Companies excelling in strategic sourcing save almost 10 to 20 times as much as it

costs to operate their sourcing operations. The study recommends that should adopt supplier relationship management strategies in order to optimize the operational and financial performance of the food and beverage firms.

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